

IMPROVEMENT OF POLYMER COATING EQUIPMENT FOR TEXTILE MATERIALS, DETERMINATION OF STRUCTURE ROLE

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Annotation. The article provides a structural diagram and the principle of operation of a device for applying and drying a polymer coating on the lines of tarpaulin materials.

Annotatsiya. Maqolada qalin materiallar choklariga polimer qoplamasini qo'llash va quritish uchun qurilmaning strukturaviy diagrammasi va ishlash printsipli keltirilgan.

Аннотация. В статье приведены структурная схема и принцип работы устройства для нанесения и сушки полимерного покрытия на линии брезентовых материалов.

Key words: roller, tarpaulin, needle, polymer, elastic cap, seam, drying, graphics, roller radius.

Kalit so'zlar: rolik, brezent, igla, polimer, elastik qopqoq, tikuv, quritish, grafik, rolik radiusi.

Ключевые слова. валик, брезент, игла, полимер, эластичный колпачок, шов, сушка, графика, радиус валика.

Introduction. In the manufacture of garments, a sealing composition based on an aqueous dispersion of acrylic copolymers is introduced to increase the tightness of their seams or in the process of thread stitching of individual seams during sewing. As a result, the material is filled with holes with a needle and the sewing thread is hydrophobized, while the appearance of the seams does not deteriorate, because the film on the surface of the thread is transparent and colorless, resembling the sealing glue inside the seam [1,2,3].

Recommended device diagram and operating principle Figure 1 shows the proposed hardware design diagram. The device works as follows. When attaching, the parts are pressed with a 12 toothed rail 15 and a pin 14 to the needle plate 17. Sliding of the fabric to the size of a needle is carried out using a toothed rail located in the holes in the needle plate. The toothed rail carries the material just below the needle 16. The direction of sliding of the material is adjusted by the seamstress while sewing. The interaction of the needle 16 and the shuttle (not shown in the picture) results in a shuttle shutter. The material to be attached then passes through the sewing machine body 1 between the upper 2 and lower 3 rollers, which are mounted on shafts 4 and 5. During the sliding of the materials, the porous surface of the polymer composite top roller 18

is conveyed through the suction tube 10 from the upper bath 8 and soaked into the upper fabric in the form of a film 13. The delivery of the polymer composition is controlled using an adjuster 11. The schematic of the equipment with a drying zone of the coated polymer is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Schematic of the equipment with a drying zone of the coated polymer

The polymer composition is soaked into the bottom layer of the materials to be bonded using 13 bottom rollers 2. The bottom roller also has a porous surface 18 and the bottom bath 9 is partially immersed in the polymer composition. During bonding, the polymer composition is applied in the form of a strip 15-20 mm wide.

Determination of the thickness of the rubber bushing of the roller with a polymer coating equipment on the seams of the tarpaulin material on the sewing machine. In the recommended equipment, rollers with a rubber bushing cover the polymer layer from above and below its seams during the movement of the tarpaulin material during operation. In this case, due to the fact that the polymer coating is partially mandatory, under the influence of compression springs and due to the total mass of the polymer on the roller axis, bushing and surface, the roller adequately covers the polymer surface. In this case, the rubber bushing of the roller is crushed and deformed. As a result, the roller rubber bushing interacts with the tarpaulin along a certain surface. The larger this surface, the larger the area of influence of the tarpaulin seams, as well as the part of the polymer coating. However, an increase in the impact area leads to an increase in the friction force and an increase in the consumption of the polymer composite[4].

Figure 2 shows the calculation scheme of the interaction of the composite roller and the tarpaulin with the welded surface.

Figure 2. Calculation polymer coating roller

scheme of the impact of the rubber bushing and tarpaulin seam surface

From the triangle AOS shown in the calculation diagram:

$$AC = \sqrt{R^2 - (R - \Delta)^2} \tag{1}$$

here, Δ - the deformation value of the roller rubber bushing, R is the outer radius of the roller. You can also write the following expressions:

$$AC = R \sin \frac{\alpha}{2}; \quad AB = 2R \sin \frac{\alpha}{2} \tag{2}$$

here, α -roller bushing deformation zone coverage angle.

From (1) and (2) obtained

$$R^2 - (R - \Delta)^2 = R^2 \sin^2 \frac{\alpha}{2} \tag{3}$$

The sum of the forces deformation of the roller rubber bush, which is affected by the compressive force through the spring and its self-gravity force on the polymer coating roller during operation, is equal to its regenerative force, ie:

$$P_{np} + g(m_{\check{y}K} + m_K + m_{\Pi L}) = \Delta C_K \tag{4}$$

here, P_{np} - the compressive strength of the springs on the roller, the C_q -roller elastic element, the coefficient of virginty of the g-rubber bushing. From the obtained expression (5) we determine the value of deformation of the roller rubber bushing.

$$\Delta = R - R \sqrt{1 - \sin^2 \frac{\alpha}{2}} \tag{6}$$

Substituting the deformation value (4) into (5), we obtain the formula for determining the coefficient of virginty of the rubber bushing of the roller.:

$$C_K = \frac{P_{np} + g(m_{\check{y}K} + m_K + m_{\Pi L})}{R(1 - \cos \frac{\alpha}{2})^2} \tag{7}$$

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